

From industrial neighbourhoods to regenerative territories: blueprinting the practices of (emerging) distributed networks of fabrication

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Abstract

Many cities across Europe, regardless of their size, face the challenge of revitalising former industrial sites. These areas, once hotspots of infrastructure, workers, and knowledge, have often been abandoned, reduced or relocated due to urban changes, and the rise of a global extractive economic model. Within this context, this article presents and discusses a set of blueprints and summarised results of nine European pilot cities that explored through the CENTRINNO H2020 European Project, different methods and strategies to support local regenerative practices by leveraging on the skills of fab labs and maker spaces as catalysts of systemic changes. The CENTRINNO pilots' blueprints represent a range of possibilities and opportunities for cities seeking to adopt regenerative practices. By delving into the challenges and journeys of the local projects connected to the maker approach, these blueprints highlight practical cases that have the potential to inspire other maker spaces and fab labs globally. They advocate for the adoption of circular economy strategies, the integration of industrial heritage elements from their locality, the promotion of alternative methods of education and the embrace of inclusiveness and equity aspects in local interventions.

Keywords

Urban regeneration, manufacturing techniques, industrial heritage, circular economy, fab labs, distributed networks

1 Situating the role of distributed networks of fabrication in neighbourhood regeneration

1.1 Regenerative processes at the neighbourhood level

Within the New European Bauhaus context, neighbourhoods were recently emphasised as an appropriate scale to envision future ways of living – placing people's needs at the heart of transformation and encouraging inclusive, beautiful and sustainable solutions through capacity building and citizen-engagement activities (*New European Bauhaus*, 2021). Neighbourhoods are identified as places to connect citizen individual transitions with the actions planned by cities and regions, that look for territorial resiliency, making gains in autonomy, fostering circular systems, and local production. This vision also aligned with the development of the self-sufficient city (Guallart, 2014) and the 15mn city that proposes

to make more accessible most daily necessities and services, such as work, shopping, education, healthcare, and leisure (*15-Minute City*, 2023).

Neighbourhoods constitute urban magmas that are shaped through the result of historic settlements by people who are living or working there. Their physical spaces are distributed among industrial, commercial or residential uses. They evolve through societal and political realities that can provoke radical changes in the landscape and the population living in the area. In particular post-industrial neighbourhoods did engage in such processes of transformation due to the extinction of industrial activities across Europe (Giraldo Nohra, 2021). When neighbourhoods are abandoned, neglected or misused, local communities could develop new activities and processes to regenerate them.

Emerging regenerative approaches are calling not only for replacing and creating something new out of the old, as it used to be. In the context of sustainability, the word 'regeneration' suggests transforming how we interact with our surroundings - place and people, and actively enhancing the health and vitality of ecosystems. Regenerative communities look to balance social needs without overshooting the planet's ecological limits. Approaches like the Doughnut framework (Raworth, 2017) can help communities to situate themselves and design actions towards what was defined as regenerative cultures (Wahl, 2016). Regeneration processes engage new dynamics with collectives, communities, and associations, contributing to projects to resist negative externalities caused by the current systems. They are long processes that highly depend on participation from citizens and local organisations, that design, make and experiment together new forms of living and making their neighbourhoods.

1.2 Distributed networks of fabrication as active players for systemic changes

Fabrication practices within neighbourhoods exhibit various facets. These practices, observed in their geographical, cultural, and historical contexts, encompass diverse forms of making. They emerge from old industrial facilities that preserve traditional techniques, industrial districts or parks, shared studios of artisans and creatives, and facilities more focused on industry 4.0 technologies. The nature of the produced goods also influences fabrication processes and their spatial distribution, as food, mobility, textiles, and construction each require different scales of production processes. In the context of nearshoring, fabrication needs to be connected through distributed networks that rely on bioregional value chains to circulate the necessary resources for productive activities. At the local scale, Fab labs and maker spaces appeared as new small-scale players in these fabrication ecosystems. They arose in various territories to respond to specific needs, sometimes sharing a common vision, and other times exhibiting slight nuances regarding their *raison d'être* and business model, being private, public, educational or commercial. As infrastructure, they provide spaces for collaborative making and exchange platforms for testing new designs, co-creating and educational activities, and promoting cooperation among stakeholders, tailored to the specific context of each location. When this happens, collaborations between local artisans or traditional manufacturers and fab labs and maker spaces generally take place by answering to technical needs such as improving certain product components or tools for production or experimenting, testing, and refining new ideas as prototypes before scaling up to production. More recently, certain fab labs and maker spaces diversified their engagement, playing roles that go beyond the appropriation of digital fabrication skills, ambitioning to act as nodes for co-designing future pathways for local production (Moritz et al., 2024), as an interface between citizens and policies (Deserti et al., 2022).

In the context of the Fab City Initiative (Diez Ladera et al., 2022), a new typology of hubs entitled "Fab City Hubs" was defined as open spaces for city-making. These hubs, also known as 'Creative and Productive Hubs', were defined as third places and meeting points for neighbours, citizens, makers, businesses, and policymakers (Ferro et al., 2022). Such hubs can be centralised and hosted in one specific fab lab or maker space, but can also be distributed, composed by fab labs, and makerspaces but also connecting with other local manufacturers and productive spaces within a neighbourhood, a city, or a region. Fab City Hubs are emerging networks of fabrication in local territories that experiment with and promote new narratives related to locally productive cities. They are embedded in larger networks of fabrication that exist in their

territory having a transformative role to play, cultivating a regenerative mindset and preserving the art of craft and fabrication by caring about the environment and about the people that are making. The present study aims to illustrate and discuss the roles played by distributed networks of fabrication in the implementation of transitions towards regenerative futures. It is hypothesised that such networks can support regenerative processes by reconnecting local productive economies with their regional and local biophysical environment, diffusing a maker culture that fosters an active role for citizens, and using open knowledge to generate skill development and job opportunities across sectors. In this paper, we present a summary of nine blueprints developed over nearly four years as part of the CENTRINNO EU project in different European cities. These blueprints, based on local networks of fabrication, encompass a wide range of actions, including the establishment of Fab City Hubs, implementation of educational programmes, deployment of social inclusion activities, research on industrial heritage and ecosystem mapping analysis to understand how cities can be more regenerative. By fostering a culture of creativity and addressing complex urban challenges, they demonstrate how local initiatives at the neighbourhood level can drive systemic change.

2 From the CENTRINNO approach to Blueprint development

2.1 The CENTRINNO approach

CENTRINNO, an EU Horizon 2020 funded project, was built upon a consortium of 26 partners with the objective of testing and demonstrating strategies for regenerating industrial historic sites into creative, locally productive, and inclusive hubs. (Centrinno Website, 2020) CENTRINNO proposed altering current organizational practices in neighbourhoods by implementing productive and creative hubs designed to address local challenges through the development of micro-missions. The project engaged nine diverse European pilot cities, ranging from big cities with populations of two million to towns with just seven thousand inhabitants. These cities included Amsterdam, Barcelona, Blonduòs, Copenhagen, Geneva, Milan, Paris, Tallinn, and Zagreb. The focus areas varied, with some targeting neighbourhoods, and others specific industrial sites or single buildings. Each city addressed different types of craftsmanship and materials, such as fashion, gardening, media production, wood, wool, and food. During 3,5 years, each city could support their transition towards regeneration through the organisation of a series of micro-missions that could facilitate the development of a common vision for the place, the building of a community and the set up of an appropriate infrastructure. Cities were empowered and trained to test, iterate and implement resources developed by a dynamic consortium. In parallel, the distributed local project, leveraging their diverse expertise, formulated bottom-up strategies, methodologies, and tools tailored to their specific needs and contextual realities. Together, CENTRINNO partners co-developed a conceptual framework of intervention, based on five guiding principles: Circular Economy, Heritage, Innovation Spaces, Learning Ecosystems (more specifically focusing on Vocational Training), and Social Inclusion (Fab Lab Barcelona., 2024), and platforms to support this framework, including the CENTRINNO Cartography (Metabolic, 2023), the Living Archive (AHK, 2023), and the FCHs toolkit for deploying Fab City Hubs (Volumes, 2023). At the end of the project, partners delivered the book entitled “Regenerative Neighborhoods in the Making” (REAL et Al., 2024) and a serie of blueprints to synthesized the results of the projects (Calvo Juarez et Al., 2024).

1.1. Blueprint proposal as a process visualisation tool

Aiming at sharing in a more understandable way allowing the replication of the outcomes generated by each pilot city, tailored blueprints were developed as simplified representations of the local project's structures. Inspired by the report “Made to Measure” (Participatory City, 2018), this visualisation tool was chosen as an alternative format to understand better the singularities that composed the overall journey of each city, acting as a comprehensive roadmap or guide detailing the most important aspects, processes and steps for the projects’ execution.

Sketching out blueprints usually creates opportunities for other ideas and connections to emerge, which can be used to develop new strategies or business propositions. Additionally, in line with systemic design and future thinking tools, blueprinting can reveal critical points and help to identify possible challenges and failures to be mitigated in future interventions (Bitner et al., 2008; Jones, 2022). In projects or initiatives addressing complex urban issues with the involvement of multiple stakeholders, this type of analysis can help reduce complexities. It offers a comprehensive overview and a simplified yet detailed view of the organizational processes needed to support the replication of activities, methodologies, or micro missions.

Designed to serve as a source of inspiration, the CENTRINNO pilot blueprints embody possibilities and potentials for cities seeking regenerative practices. By delving into the nine pilot initial challenges and journeys, we look at tailored bottom-up strategies, activities and tools applied towards innovation, creativity and sustainable local dynamics. Simultaneously, practical cases that hold the potential to inspire policy recommendations were identified together with guidelines on governance transition and circular practices towards regenerative ecosystems.

2.2 Blueprint design and data collection of distributed networks of fabrication

The CENTRINNO pilots' blueprints encapsulate a summarised version of the main micro-missions, journeys and outputs achieved by nine European cities in addressing the initial challenges and established expected impacts. For the development of this content, an analysis process was conducted closely with the main partners of each local project to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the selected data. Initial drafts were shared and individual meetings were convened to reflect on the broader trajectory of the pilots' journey. These discussions focused on the necessary steps and activities to achieve replicable outputs, as well as exploring prospective tools and inspiration for shaping new policies. Revolving around a productive 'making' approach that empowers citizens and engages local producers and creatives, the CENTRINNO project was based on a consortium composed of many organizations represented by fab labs, design studios and innovation centres. Following the strategy of fostering regenerative practices developed in diverse local contexts, special attention was given to identifying the variety of "making" techniques and methodologies applied across the different activities. Ranging from product creation, demonstrators, training courses, and practical tools, the selected activities explored materials such as textiles, packaging, wood, plastics, water or food. Additionally, insights on the establishment of concrete collaborations were mapped, including data about public-private partnerships and agreements among stakeholders to strengthen collective achievements. This multidisciplinary stakeholder approach guided the discussions centred on how creativity and regenerative practices can be considered as sources of inspiration for shaping new bottom-up policy recommendations.

The CENTRINNO pilots' blueprints data collection followed a participatory approach based on existing data captured through the pilot's micro missions and a validation of the representative participants of each location (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Simplified overview of the CENTRINNO pilots' blueprint approach

The blueprint structure is based on four main sections of data descriptions composed by:

Pilot ID: Including a vision of the local project, a historical description of the pilot area, a map representing the area of the pilot, key performance indicators accomplished and characteristics such as the city's population density, the pilot scale and their productive focus.

Pilots Journey: Describing a summary of the main activities and micro-missions distributed across the three sprints of activities categorized by the five CENTRINNO key concepts (Circular Economy, Heritage, Social Inclusion & Innovation Spaces, and Vocational Training). For each sprint, four primary stages of actions were selected representing activities related to mapping, engaging, prototyping and developing, culminating in a replication stage after the process.

Pilots Tools: Showcasing two main tools created and used by each pilot city. Nevertheless, each pilot city developed many tools during the project's course, and they are all available on the CENTRINNO Fab City Hub Toolkit (FCH Toolkit) with full details.

Practical cases and policy briefs: Based on bottom-up policy recommendations as an alternative to traditional policy development approaches. The policy briefs were based on the learning gathered through practical cases linked to eight primary areas of influence for policy briefs, namely *Heritage value and innovation, Policy-making mindsets, Contingency and macro trends, Spatial Planning and Urban Development Frameworks, Regulation, Funding, and Knowledge & Capacities*. In the following table, a summary of each pilot city blueprint is represented by highlighting their different contexts, connected to selected former industrial zones, their main micro-missions, expressed by the activities developed as part of their journeys, a selection of tools developed by the local teams and policy briefs focuses aimed at promoting local regenerative practices.

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Figure 2. Illustrations of the CENTRINNO pilots' blueprint

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Table 1: Comparison of blueprints in the nine pilots, extracted from the report of Blueprints and Policy development guidelines for replicability and wider use

	Context	Main Outputs	Policy Briefs
Description	Description of the pilot's geographical and cultural context	Three main results developed by each pilot can be replicated by other cities, practitioners and organizations	Set of policy recommendations based on the knowledge gathered during the pilots' micro-missions development
Amsterdam	Known for shipbuilding and repair, the neighbourhood of Amsterdam Noord has emerged as a hub for circular activities and innovation. Pressing the need for housing has led to the conversion of remaining industrial land into residential use, challenges such as the termination of rental contracts for small businesses and makers. low availability of green spaces, industrial pollution and gentrification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of Platform Maatschap Amsterdam, an alliance aimed at addressing the challenges faced by makers in the city - Exhibition 'Makers van Noord' placing craftsmanship in the spotlight - Professionalising teachers through a monthly education programme on circular entrepreneurship and circular making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing policies that incentivize the repurposing of existing spaces into affordable workshops or studios for makers and craftspeople • Establishing mechanisms for community involvement in shaping policies that directly impact the maker community.
Barcelona	Known as the 'Catalan Manchester' for its 19th and early 20th-century textile industry, Poblenou has been a testing ground for various urban projects, including the 1992 Olympic game, and the 22@District initiative. El Poblenou embodies a crucial part of Barcelona's industrial heritage, continually attracting new technological companies to the district, while artists, local makers, manufacturers, and artisans fight to keep its productive identity towards more socially engaged and circular practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch of the Network of Productive Hubs of Barcelona and Involvement of makers, manufacturers and creative spaces to the online platform Make Works Catalonia - Development of 2 editions of vocational course for professors and the CENTRINNO School Hackathon - Development of the exhibition Fabrica Poblenou with co-designed and upcycled wood and textile artefacts hosted in collaboration with the city. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valorizing local talents by encouraging collaborative initiatives between local artisans, designers, and makers to create sustainable design solutions. • Emphasizing the importance of inclusivity by involving citizens, educational institutions, businesses, associations, and the wider community. • Encouraging the use of leftover materials and local resources within urban landscapes to foster a culture of locally sourced and produced materials.
Blönduós	Northwest Iceland has a long background as an agricultural region and faces challenges such as limited employment diversity, a trend of youth migration, and depopulation. Blönduós houses the Icelandic Textile Centre, which is dedicated to promoting textile innovation, knowledge-building, and local production. At the Icelandic Textile Center, traditional handcrafts seamlessly blend with 21st-century skills, contributing to the region's economic development and preserving its cultural heritage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Format of local exhibition to be replicated - Textile businesses, new products ("Cool Wool Box, "Snoðbreiða") and processes (bacteria dye), student final projects developed - New innovation space established in Northwest: the Textile Lab - Opportunities to connect training in traditional handcrafts, textile innovation, creative sustainability and business management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing and promoting creative labs as enabling spaces for circular transitions within the Textile and Clothing (T&C) sector, encouraging innovation and sustainable methods. • Making accessible education to all, actively addressing and dismantling gender disparities to create a more inclusive workforce. • Strengthening the values associated with historical traditions, heritage cultural identity and traditional craftsmanship embedded at regional sites.

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	Context	Main Outputs	Policy Briefs
Copenhagen	Copenhagen is under intense pressure for redevelopment and a housing and rental market with rapidly increasing prices. Rentemestervej used to be an important industrial and manufacturing centre of the city for more than 100 years has undergone a transformation into offices and studios, illustrating the swift repurposing of available spaces in the neighbourhood. The ownership of these formerly industrial sites, distinguished by their heritage status, is now distributed among small businesses, fostering the potential for a collaborative space-sharing economy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of a joint platform/network for local stakeholders - The establishment of a fund by the municipality to support creative industries and urban environments - Design and crafts workshops open to the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a comprehensive understanding of the current creative ecosystem and implementing measures aimed at retaining and fostering the vital urban environments • Building robust relations within the municipality fostering collaborations to create a unified approach towards supporting and promoting creative initiatives • Communicating the urban planning agenda through analysis and events ensuring it resonates with stakeholders, policymakers, and the wider community.
Geneva	The Zone Industrielle de Charmilles, known as "ZIC," was once a centre for industrial activities that manufactured precision physical instruments, textiles, and watchmaking. Today, it has evolved into a hub for small and medium-sized enterprises specializing in both traditional and digital craft production, including wood- and metalworking. In Geneva, the ZIC serves various roles as a local production centre, a nexus for local materials, and a hub for repair and reuse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General governance model, administrative and financial management of the MACO Hub - Documentation of a programme for reintegration focused on craftsmanship and digital fabrication - The "Green Friday" event model promotes small business, local products and the circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building up expertise for cooperation development and adaptive reuse in ephemeral or abandoned old buildings • Implementing strategies promoting dialogue and shared decision-making among stakeholders involved in repurposing projects by ensuring equitable participation and consensus-building. • Strengthening programs for reskilling and attracting people towards local and circular production, encouraging the development of curriculum tailored to the needs of evolving industries.
Milan	Located in central Milan, Porta Genova is vital to the circular economy, focusing on repair, reuse, and innovation. The Ex-Ansaldo factory, once an electromechanical plant, now serves as a cultural and creative hub. Owned by the Milan municipality, this historic site is undergoing urban regeneration to foster new forms of production and craftsmanship. Programs promoting digital manufacturing and innovative craftsmanship aim to create jobs, revitalize suburbs, and foster social cohesion.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Draft a strategic plan for advancing the circular economy in fashion and design within Milan Municipality - Establishment of the platform Manifattura di Milano dedicated to craftsmanship, urban manufacturing and circular economy in the fashion and design sectors - 'Percorsi Urbani Circolari' learning journey as a skill set required to adopt circular practices at the urban level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering partnerships between the public and private sectors to create shared spaces or repurpose underutilized buildings • Encouraging the provision of affordable, long-term spaces specifically allocated for local enterprises within the city by establishing designated zones or buildings where such activities can operate with reasonable rents and secure leases. • Supporting businesses in temporary locations to transition smoothly to permanent spaces preserving the established networks and communities they've built.

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	Context	Main Outputs	Policy Briefs
Paris	The 18th Arrondissement of Paris is a diverse, densely populated neighbourhood facing challenges like limited green space, pollution, gentrification risk, and high unemployment. As a circular city model, it serves as a production centre, loop closer, and innovation hub. A renovated brutalist building, now a co-working space, exemplifies this transformation. Owned by the City Council, it offers potential for urban gardening and the revival of historical gardening techniques, enhancing its cultural and industrial landscape.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opening of an experimental farm on the roof of a building to test how robotics can contribute to the regeneration of the French method - Development of the Food Track digital platform for sharing tools or urban farming - Guidance on how to create a FoodLab in a Fab City Hub - Developing joint projects on distributed production, and vocational training courses on circular design and food production such as the training program 'Resiliences productives' 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrating the sustainability of alternative economic models such as shared professional kitchens and complementary infrastructures to help companies design, prototype and test their ideas. • Getting financial accessibility to the real estate market through public or private partnerships considering temporary use convention • Encouraging hubs to develop strong identities centred around social economy and ecological transition
Tallinn	Kopli, a subdistrict located in northern Tallinn, bears historical and industrial significance, tracing its origins back to the early 20th century when it served as a Russian shipyard. The Kopli district plays a vital role as both a production centre and a loop closer to the circular city framework. Significant architectural revitalization began with the Russian Empire's naval base. Notably, Kopli 93, an Art Deco building from 1936, now a heritage site, serves as an innovative hub for traditional skills, local food production, and peer production.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Podcasts, awareness and reach around circularity - GranMother workshops and a Grandfather corner, a grandfather-style working station for woodworking, leveraging techniques used in the past - Replicability of a networking platform for many resilience, environmental, and social gatherings - Establishment of educational programs and learning days for local citizens, and university students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a platform for the emergence of ideas from communities, ensuring representation and sustainability of projects realisation • Implementing robust evaluation mechanisms to assess the impact and effectiveness of funded projects. • Establishing platforms for sharing success stories, best practices, and lessons learned from the participatory budgeting program.
Zagreb	Sesvete, Zagreb's largest area, faces challenges such as limited green spaces, asbestos in former factories, and illegal waste disposal. The abandoned Sljeme, a former meat factory and pig farm, played a key role in the Balkan meat industry. Post-privatization mismanagement led to its bankruptcy in 2006. Owned by the municipality since 2017, Sljeme offers high potential for urban regeneration and repurposing due to its excellent rail and future road network connections.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report of new circular construction opportunities for concrete reuse of building materials - Strategies to foster engagement between local actors and larger networks at a city, national, and European level - Curriculum of a Program tested for future use at the Fab City Hub Sesvete and a national level with 5 module course on design thinking, digital tools and fusion processes with traditional heritage skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivating enduring relationships with public bodies, emphasizing the long-term benefits and community impact of projects such as Fab City Hubs • Facilitating national and international synergies to act as a catalyst of good practices, attract globally (global and local) cooperation and foster mutual learning • Designing and sharing viable and inspiring pathways for old industrial buildings at the intersection between urban mining, a museum of stories and a place for learning and prototyping

The full CENTRINNO pilots' blueprints are available online: <https://zenodo.org/records/12733634>

3 Concluding remarks and learnings for future prospects

3.1 Nine journeys as sources of inspiration and elements of discussion to build future interventions in neighbourhoods

The blueprint methodology offered a comprehensive visualisation of how local interventions can support systemic changes and the resiliency of neighbourhoods. Besides the added value created through the many micro missions, significant changes were possible to be identified in the different urban contexts explored by the project. In Amsterdam, consistently raising awareness for difficult situations encountered by the local makers of Amsterdam Noord, due to the gentrification process and the recent urbanistic plans in the area, led to increased interest and support from policymakers. This approach emphasised the importance of consistent advocacy to influence policy changes and secure a supportive environment for local initiatives. In Barcelona, sustained activities, including participatory workshops, talks and exhibitions, fostered the development of a collaborative network of productive spaces, proving that regular engagement and opportunities can create a strong, trust-based community and enhance public-private sector relations. In Blönduós, the establishment of a creative textile hub with strong local and international partnerships and educational programmes boosted team confidence and attracted positive feedback, illustrating the importance of building solid foundations and networks for long-term success. In Copenhagen, the creation of a dedicated municipal fund, coupled with strategic influence on relevant policies, provided sustained financial support and political focus for creative industries and urban environments. In Geneva, the focus on fostering collaborations and engaging in dialogue about heritage and alternative ways of local production helped the establishment of a shared value of preserving local manufacturing. These actions underscored the commitment to innovative solutions and community engagement while creating connections with the Municipality of Geneva in the development of policy plans for regenerative futures. In Milan, increased ecosystem collaboration and political backing strengthened circular economy initiatives, showing that learning journeys, collective effort but also a hybrid infrastructure, such as the Manifattura di Milano platform, can enhance local craftsmanship and urban manufacturing. In Paris, the establishment of solid connections with the City of Paris led to the implementation of the Fab City Hub Paris, the development of urban gardening projects and projects on inclusivity, underscoring the impact of strong public-private collaborations and addressing social involvement. In Tallinn, the success in revitalising an abandoned cultural house in Northern Tallinn and transforming it into a functioning community hub (Kopli 93), supported the establishment of a public-private partnership with the Municipality. The City Hall took over the space management ensuring long-term sustainability while fostering a sense of trust and community creation, core values upheld by the local team throughout the project. In Zagreb, the ability to navigate obstacles and seek new funding opportunities demonstrated strategic adaptation in response to evolving policies and project needs. Challenges were addressed through community engagement, strategic events, and resilient network-building.

3.2 Blueprints as a reflection tool for future fabrication ecosystems

Blueprinting the work conducted during the regenerative journeys of local networks over an extended period presented challenges in data collection and validation from participants, as well as the need for comprehensive and accessible data visualization for a diverse audience. This process initiated new dialogues with participants from local city pilots, facilitating a better understanding of both quantitative and qualitative data and highlighting the main outcomes of each pilot. It also fostered peer-learning exchanges within the project consortium, enhancing exploitation strategies.

Although it drastically simplified the design processes, the blueprint format was chosen to make visible the complexity and interdependencies behind each pilot, allowing the possibility of understanding how

different processes contributed to achieving concrete indicators. The format aimed to be accessible for quick reading, providing easy access to the main information with clear visual elements, while also supporting deeper reading by sharing more detailed information necessary for researchers or future replicators.

The comprehensibility of the blueprints, as tools for dissemination and replication, will be further tested in future workshops targeting wider audiences, such as policymakers and other makerspaces. Complementary formats could be considered in future works to retrace and envision regenerative design pathways, including short multimedia performances, visualisation tools, reflective podcasts or written essays.

3.3 Gaps and opportunities for distributed networks of fabrication

The study demonstrated the need for creating alliances at local scales to face both socio-ecological and economic challenges. In the diverse contexts explored, stakeholders used to bond together for multiple reasons: lack of affordability due to gentrification, local production market degradation, implementation of circular practices, and heritage preservation. By acting together, they aim to create local conditions for locally sustainable production practices to flourish, rather than seeing the disappearance of practical knowledge and dedicated infrastructures.

The blueprints showed that the distributed networks of fabrication can act from diverse prisms to foster local transformations. They contribute to mapping local resources and connecting circular urban ecosystems. They share local stories of making and curate exhibitions with their community of makers and citizens to share and discuss cultural representations of making from the past to the future. They work together with schools and social integration organisations to transmit intergenerational educational programs to transmit skills and new vocations. They rehabilitate abandoned spaces into physical hubs that foster creativity, social inclusion, infrastructure and knowledge sharing.

Important gaps were identified when fab labs and maker spaces were at the core of the establishment of distributed networks of fabrication, inviting future facilitators of such networks to consider engagement strategies and contribute to organisational and policy changes.

Fostering cooperation over competition mindset between local maker spaces

Distributed networks of fabrication are emerging among stakeholders that have their own beliefs, values, their own stories and a path of development that comes with the nuance of previous relationships. In some contexts, they could act as competitors as they share common service offers. This involves the need to create bridges among people and spaces to express their differences, to then build a common vision and engage them through projects and missions.

Building trust with local manufacturers

To build a real impact at the local scale, it is important to look outside what is called the “maker bubble” and onboard with local manufacturers in the network. In CENTRINNO, efforts were made to understand the current practices, their needs and their appeal to engage with such networks. Facilitators should adopt a humble posture, learn from them, build trust over time and propose win-win activities, avoiding them running time-consuming projects that can slow down their activity. The collection of stories in the CENTRINNO Living Archive and throughout the Make Works platform (*Find Local Manufacturers in Your Region | Make Works*, n.d.) were particularly appreciated as alternative dissemination tools that share a common narrative around local fabrication.

Consolidating relationships with local and regional public bodies

The way public bodies such as city councils are supporting the establishment of distributed networks of fabrication is a determinant for generating local impacts. It was shown in CENTRINNO, that the presence of the municipality as a supportive partner in certain pilots has allowed the connection of micro missions with the urban agendas. When city agendas are aligned with the vision of the network of fabrication, the latter is acting as frontrunners, paving the way for emerging new practices and bonds. Still, relationships

with public organisations are consolidated in the long term, strengthened according to the perceived legitimacy by policymakers, and strongly fluctuating according to political context changes.

Reinforcing the resonance with bioregional realities

Once passed the initiation of the networks, stating sustainable values and a vision towards territorial regeneration, high risks of diluting environmental engagement are present, due to short-term objectives for engaging, fabricating, and communicating. Facilitating such networks is acting as guardians of sustainability, making environmental data more accessible, proposing spaces for knowledge transmission and debates, opting for informed decision-making processes, and sharing community experiences in connection with the local environment. Opportunities are rising such as expanding the notion of networks to non-humans, including biophysical components or manufacturing goods and services, and integrating them into the governance models.

To conclude, the blueprints add to the current resources developed by the Fab City Network. Authors encourage the Fab community to read and use them to foster knowledge exchange in their local communities and to build up new peer-learning opportunities.

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